

Formulation And Development of an Ivermectin Nanoemulgel for Topical Treatment of Rosacea

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ABSTRACT

To formulate and evaluate an ivermectin nanoemulgel for effective topical treatment of rosacea by improving solubility, skin penetration, and drug release. A nanoemulsion was formulated using liquid paraffin (oil phase), Span 20 and Tween 20 (surfactant and co-surfactant), and polyethylene glycol. This nanoemulsion was incorporated into a gel base using Carbopol 940 to form a nanoemulgel. The optimized batch (F3) was evaluated for particle size, zeta potential, polydispersity index (PDI), pH, drug content, thermal behavior by DSC, and in vitro diffusion study, 97.45% release at 240mins. The ivermectin nanoemulgel showed enhanced solubility, good physicochemical properties, and sustained drug release, indicating its potential for effective topical treatment of rosacea.

Keywords: Ivermectin, nanoemulgel, topical delivery, rosacea, skin penetration, drug release..

INTRODUCTION

Rosacea is a prevalent chronic inflammatory skin disorder that primarily impacts the central area of the face, with a higher incidence in women compared to men¹. The pathophysiology remains partially unclear; however, alterations in the immune system, along with modifications in both the nervous and vascular systems, have been recognized. Additionally, the microbes associated with normal skin flora, particularly those found within the pilo-sebaceous unit, such as Demodex mites and Staphylococcus epidermidis, may serve as potential triggers for rosacea^{2,3}. Initially, symptoms are transient, followed by persistent erythema resulting from repeated vasodilation. This is then accompanied by telangiectasia and skin inflammation, which manifests as papules, pustules, lymphoedema, and fibrosis⁴.

Emulgels are emulsions, which can be either of the oil-in-water or water-in-oil type, that are gelled through the incorporation of a gelling agent. An emulsified gel is stable and serves as a superior vehicle for hydrophobic or poorly water-soluble drugs. In short, emulgels represent a combination of emulsion and gel⁵. Emulsions exhibit a certain degree of elegance and can be easily washed off whenever necessary. They also possess a high capacity to penetrate the skin. Emulgels intended for dermatological applications have several advantageous properties, including being thixotropic, greaseless, easily spreadable, easily removable, emollient, non-staining, and transparent, along with a long shelf life and an appealing appearance⁶. Formulations that incorporate Nano emulsion within a gel base are referred to as nanoemulgels. This involves the integration of a Nano emulsion system into a gel matrix, which enhances skin permeation⁷. This combination of nanoemulgels

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functions as drug reservoirs, facilitating the transfer of the drug from the inner phase to the outer phase and beyond. When nanoemulgel comes into contact with the skin, it releases oil droplets from the gel, allowing these droplets to penetrate the stratum corneum (SC) of the skin and deliver the drug to the targeted site. Nanoemulsion-gels exhibit excellent adhesion properties, and the high solubilization of the drug in the oil phase results in a greater concentration gradient towards the skin, thereby further enhancing drug penetration. Additionally, patient compliance is improved due to the increased spreadability compared to creams and ointments, along with a reduction in stickiness⁸. The objective of this study was to formulate and enhance a nanoemulgel formulation of Ivermectin for effective topical application. Ivermectin is a broad-spectrum anti-parasitic drug. It is primarily utilized in humans for the treatment of onchocerciasis, but it is also effective against various other worm infections, including Strongyloidiasis, ascariasis, trichuriasis, and enterobiasis. Topical application of ivermectin has shown greater efficacy in treating papulopustular rosacea⁹.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Ivermectin was obtained from Yarrow Chem Products, Mumbai. Excipients including Carbopol 940 (used as a gelling agent), Span 20 and Tween 20 (used as emulsifiers), Liquid Paraffin (used as the oil phase), Propylene Glycol and Ethanol (used as co-

solvent and penetration enhancers) were purchased from Research Lab Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. All excipients were of analytical grade.

Preparation of Ivermectin nano-emulgel

1. Drug Loading and Nanoemulsion Preparation.

Ivermectin is dissolved in ethanol. Liquid paraffin and Span 20 are heated to approximately 70°C, followed by the addition of the ivermectin-ethanol solution. Tween 20 is heated in 5 ml of purified water at around 70°C. The oil phase is then gradually introduced into the aqueous phase while employing high-speed homogenization (5000–10000 rpm) for a duration of 15 minutes. Ultrasonication is performed for 5–10 minutes¹⁰.

2. Preparation of Gel

Carbopol 940 is dispersed in 10 ml of purified water and allowed to swell for 30 minutes. Propylene glycol is added and mixed thoroughly¹¹.

3. Incorporation Nanoemulsion into Gel Formation

The nanoemulsion is slowly incorporated into the gel base while stirring at 500 rpm. The pH is adjusted to 6.5–6.8 using TEA. The mixture is homogenized at 500 rpm for 15 minutes to achieve a uniform gel¹².

Table: 1 Different formulation of Ivermectin Nanoemulgel (% w/w)

Formulation	Ivermectin (mg)	Carbopol 940	Liquid paraffin	Span 20	Tween 20	Propylene glycol	Water
F1	500	0.5	5	2	5	5	100
F2	500	0.5	5	2	10	5	100
F3	500	1	10	4	5	5	100
F4	500	1	10	4	10	5	100
F5	500	1.5	5	2	5	5	100
F6	500	1.5	5	2	10	5	100

EVALUATION OF NANO-EMULGEL:

(a) **Physical appearance:** The prepared emulgels were assessed for their color, consistency, homogeneity, and texture after a 24-hour period of preparation¹³.

(b) **Determination of pH:** A calibrated pH meter was utilized to measure the pH values of 1% aqueous solutions of the prepared emulgels¹⁴.

(c) **Washability:** The formulations were applied to the skin, and the ease and extent of washing with water were evaluated manually, with observations recorded¹⁵.

- (d) Extrudability study:** The emulgel formulations were filled into collapsible metal tubes or aluminium collapsible tubes. The tubes were pressed to extrude the material and the extrudability of the formulation was checked¹⁶.
- (e) Spreadability Test:** Two glass slides (6 × 2 cm) were used. The emulgel was placed between the slides and compressed under a 100 g weight to form a thin layer. After removing the weight and scraping excess emulgel, the lower slide was fixed, and the upper slide was attached to a string carrying a 20 g load. The time required for the upper slide to move 6 cm and separate was recorded. The test was repeated six times and the average was calculated. Spreadability (S) was determined by the formula: $S = m \times l / t$. Where, S = Spreadability (cm/sec), m = weight tied to the upper Slide (20 grams), l = length of glass slide (6 cms), t = time taken in seconds¹⁷.
- (f) Viscosity:** The viscosity of the formulated gel was assessed utilizing a Brookfield digital Viscometer (spindle no. 6, 10 rpm) at a temperature of $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The gel was transferred into a wide-mouth container to ensure adequate spindle immersion. The samples were permitted to settle for 30 minutes at a stable temperature prior to measurement¹⁸.
- (g) Determination of % drug content:** 1 g of nanoemulgel is mixed with 25 ml of methanol. This solution is sonicated for 30 minutes. Drug content is calculated using a suitable analytical method from this solution. Drug content (mg) = concentration × dilution factor % Drug content = drug content (mg) ÷ label claim (mg)¹⁹.
- (h) In vitro drug release studies :** A cellophane membrane (25 × 2 cm) was washed under running water and soaked in distilled water for 24 hours to remove residual glycerine and enhance permeability. For the in-vitro diffusion study of the nanoemulgel, one gram of the formulation was applied to the prehydrated membrane, which was securely affixed to one end of a vertical glass diffusion cell (15 mm internal diameter, 100 mm height). The cell was inverted and immersed in 250 ml of freshly prepared phosphate buffer (pH 5.4) maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, with continuous magnetic stirring. At predetermined time intervals, 5 ml aliquots were withdrawn and replaced with fresh buffer to maintain sink conditions. Samples were suitably diluted and analyzed at 245 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, with phosphate buffer as blank²⁰.
- (i) Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) :** Potassium bromide (KBr) was first dried in a hot air oven at 105°C for 2–3 hours. Approximately 600 mg of dried KBr was finely ground using a mortar and pestle. About 50 mg of the sample was added to the KBr and triturated to obtain a homogeneous mixture. The mixture was compressed into a transparent pellet and scanned using an FTIR spectrophotometer in the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} ²¹.
- (j) Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) :** A differential scanning calorimetry study was conducted to assess the thermal behavior of the formulation. Nearly 5 mg of the sample was accurately weighed and sealed in an aluminum pan. The analysis was carried out over a temperature range of 30°C to 300°C , with a constant heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under a nitrogen atmosphere. An empty sealed aluminum pan served as the reference. Thermograms were evaluated to detect any possible interactions or changes in thermal properties²².
- (k) Particle Size and Polydispersity Index (PDI):** Particle size analysis of the nanoemulsion formulation was carried out using a Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) technique with the HORIBA SZ-100 instrument. The measurement was performed at 25.2°C using a 90° scattering angle²³.
- (l) Zeta Potential:** Zeta potential measurement was carried out using the same HORIBA SZ-100 instrument at 25°C to evaluate the surface charge and stability of the nanoemulsion²⁴.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present work was aimed to enhance skin penetration through the formulation of a nanoemulgel. The prepared formulations were characterized by

evaluating their physical appearance, pH, spreadability, viscosity, drug content, and in-vitro drug release.

Table 2: Physical appearance

Formulation	Washability	Extrudability	Observation	Clogging	Homogeneity
F1	+++	++	White cream	Absent	Good
F2	+++	++	White cream	Absent	Good
F3	+++	+++	White cream	Absent	Good
F4	+++	+++	White cream	Absent	Good
F5	+++	+	White cream	Present	Average
F6	+++	+	White cream	Present	Average

Excellent: +++, Good: ++, Average: +, Poor: -

All the prepared formulations were observed to be white in appearance. Clogging was absent in all formulations except F5 and F6, which showed slight clogging. Homogeneity was found to be good for F1

to F4, while F5 and F6 showed average homogeneity. Washability was excellent (+++) in all except F6, which showed good washability (++) and extrudability ranged from good to excellent across formulations.

Table 3: Results of Viscosity, pH, % Drug content and Spreadability

Formulation	Viscosity (cps)	PH	Spreadability (gcm/sec)
F1	3265	6.92	13.56
F2	3345	5.99	12.78
F3	4214	6.45	14.65
F4	4315	6.68	11.45
F5	4522	6.77	13.25
F6	4598	5.98	12.78

The spreadability of F1 to F6 was found to be 13.56, 12.78, 14.65, 11.45, 13.25, and 12.78 gcm/sec respectively. The pH values of the formulations ranged from 5.98 to 6.92, which is close to skin pH,

indicating suitability for topical application. The viscosity of the formulations ranged from 3265 cps (F1) to 4598 cps (F6), showing gradual increase across batches.

Figure.1 % Drug content

%Drug content: The drug content of all formulations was found to be within acceptable range, with F3 showing the highest drug content 98.12% among all,

indicating uniform drug distribution in the formulation.

In-vitro drug release:

Figure.2 In-vitro drug release study

The in-vitro drug release study was performed for all formulations (F1–F6) over a period of 240 minutes. The cumulative % drug release at 240 minutes was found to be 99% (F1), 98.2% (F2), 97.45% (F3), 98.6% (F4), 91.85% (F5), and 89.4% (F6). Among all,

formulation F3 showed a consistent and controlled release pattern, achieving 97.45% drug release at 240 minutes, indicating it as the optimized batch. The sustained release profile of F3 suggests better drug retention and prolonged therapeutic action compared to other formulations.

Table 4. In-vitro drug release data of batch f3

Time (min)	%drug release
0	0
15	30.15
30	45.21
45	55.45
60	68.75
120	81
240	97.45

Figure. 3 In-vitro drug release study of optimize batch f3

The optimized batch F3 of nanoemulgel showed good drug release of 97.45% after 4 hours, indicating controlled drug release suitable for prolonged therapeutic effect.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) study:

Figure.4 FTIR of Nano-emulsion formulation

FTIR spectroscopy was performed to confirm the compatibility and chemical stability of ivermectin in the nanostructured formulation. A broad peak between 3360–3550 cm^{-1} indicated O–H stretching, suggesting the presence of hydrophilic components like water, propylene glycol, or Tween. Peaks at 2854 cm^{-1} and 2924 cm^{-1} correspond to aliphatic C–H stretching, likely from oily excipients. A strong absorption at $\sim 1734 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirmed C=O stretching

from ester or ketone groups present in ivermectin. The region between 1540–1650 cm^{-1} showed N–H bending or C=C stretching, indicating possible drug-polymer interactions. Peaks in the 1050–1100 cm^{-1} range were attributed to C–O–C stretching, consistent with ether linkages. No significant shifts were observed in the fingerprint region ($\sim 406 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), confirming the structural integrity of the drug.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) :

Figure.5 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The DSC analysis of the ivermectin nanoemulsion shows an endothermic peak at 82.74°C, significantly lower than the pure drug's melting point of around 155°C. This shift, along with the absence of a sharp

peak at 155°C, indicates that ivermectin is no longer in its crystalline form but is molecularly dispersed or in an amorphous state within the nanoemulsion. These findings confirm the successful formation of a stable

ivermectin nanoemulsion with improved drug solubilization. **Particle Size Analysis:**

Figure.6 Particle Size

The particle size analysis of the optimized ivermectin Nano-emulsion revealed a mean particle size of 8.4 nm, with a Z-Average of 2.4 nm and a polydispersity index (PDI) of 0.618, indicating a nanometric and moderately uniform dispersion. The sharp peak

observed between 6–10 nm further confirmed the narrow size distribution, making the formulation suitable for topical delivery due to enhanced penetration potential.

Zeta Potential Analysis

Figure.7 Zeta Potential

Zeta potential measurement showed a value of +35.0 mV, suggesting good colloidal stability and low tendency for particle aggregation. The presence of multiple peaks at +58.9 mV, -60.6 mV, and +102.2 mV indicates heterogeneous surface charge distributions, likely due to surfactants or stabilizers. The overall positive charge confirms a cationic nature of the formulation, which may enhance interaction

with the negatively charged skin surface and improve therapeutic efficacy.

CONCLUSION

The optimized ivermectin nanoemulgel (Batch F3) demonstrated excellent physicochemical and diffusion characteristics suitable for topical delivery. The formulation exhibited a nanometric particle size

(mean 8.4 nm), good electrostatic stability (+35.0 mV zeta potential), and moderate uniformity (PDI 0.618). DSC analysis confirmed that ivermectin was present in a non-crystalline, molecularly dispersed state. The pH (6.45) and high drug content (98.12%) ensure compatibility and potency of the formulation. In vitro diffusion studies showed sustained drug release, with 97.45% drug release at 240 minutes. Overall, the nanoemulgel holds significant promise as an effective topical delivery system for ivermectin.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to this study.

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